

Marketing

UDK 659.113:338.48:316.628

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15476750>

The impact of visual content from drones on the behavior of potential customers in the field of hotel marketing

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Accepted:07.05.2025 | Published: 20.05.2025

Abstract. The hospitality industry is undergoing profound transformations related to the development of digital technologies, changing consumer behavioral patterns, and growing requirements for personalization of marketing communications. In this context, the role of visual content as a means of creating an emotional connection with the client at the stage of familiarization with the service is growing. The **purpose** of the study is to determine the impact of visual content created with the help of drones on the behavior of potential customers in the field of hotel marketing, as well as to assess its effectiveness as a tool for stimulating demand and emotional engagement of consumers. **Methods.** The study uses an interdisciplinary approach, which includes the analysis of scientific sources, generalization of practical experience in the implementation of visual content in digital marketing of hotels, structural and logical modeling of the impact of drone video on customer behavior, as well as content analysis of digital promotion channels (social networks, booking platforms, websites, etc.). **Results.** It has been established that videos from drones activate the emotional perception of the offer, build trust, and create a positive brand image. The advantages and challenges of

introducing drone technologies in the hospitality field are systematized. Digital channels of marketing communication in the hotel business are analyzed; the key elements of visual content from drones in hotel marketing have been identified; the psychological and communication effects that drone content causes in consumers and the behavioral reactions of potential customers to drone videos have been studied; strategic approaches to the use of drones in hotel marketing have been studied; A model of the influence of video from drones on customer behavior is proposed. **Conclusions.** Visual content from drones is a practical element of hotel marketing, which significantly changes approaches to promoting and consuming hotel services. Further implementation of such solutions requires the integration of digital competencies in the professional training of marketers, adapting strategies to the target audience, and using creative methods of personalized content. The scripted approach to the video and the technical characteristics of the device determine the effectiveness of drone visual content. The integration of high-tech equipment will create a competitive video product that enhances the marketing impact on different target audience segments. This opens up new opportunities for building an image, building trust, and stimulating action, particularly booking.

Keywords: hotel marketing, drone content, consumer behavior, digital advertising.

Вплив візуального контенту з дронів на поведінку потенційних клієнтів у сфері готельного маркетингу

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Анотація. Індустрія гостинності переживає глибокі трансформації, пов'язані з розвитком цифрових технологій, зміною поведінкових патернів

споживачів та зростанням вимог до персоналізації маркетингових комунікацій. У цьому контексті зростає роль візуального контенту як засобу створення емоційного зв'язку з клієнтом ще на етапі ознайомлення з послугою. **Метою** дослідження є визначення впливу візуального контенту, створеного за допомогою дронів, на поведінку потенційних клієнтів у сфері готельного маркетингу, а також оцінка його ефективності як інструменту стимулювання попиту та емоційного залучення споживачів. **Методи.** У дослідженні використано міждисциплінарний підхід, який включає аналіз наукових джерел, узагальнення практичного досвіду впровадження візуального контенту в цифровому маркетингу готелів, структурно-логічне моделювання впливу дрон-відео на поведінку клієнтів, а також контент-аналіз цифрових каналів просування (соціальні мережі, платформи бронювання, сайти тощо). **Результати.** Встановлено, що відео з дронів активізують емоційне сприйняття пропозиції, формують довіру та позитивний імідж бренду. Систематизовано переваги й виклики впровадження дрон-технологій у сфері гостинності. Проаналізовано цифрові канали маркетингової комунікації у готельному бізнесі; визначено ключові елементи візуального контенту у готельному маркетингу; досліджено психологічні та комунікаційні ефекти, які викликає дрон-контент у споживача та поведінкові реакції потенційних клієнтів на відео; досліджено стратегічні підходи використання дронів у готельному маркетингу; запропоновано модель впливу відео з дронів на поведінку клієнта. **Висновки.** Візуальний контент з дронів є дієвим елементом готельного маркетингу, який суттєво змінює підходи до просування та споживання готельних послуг. Подальше впровадження таких рішень потребує інтеграції цифрових компетенцій у фаховій підготовці маркетологів, адаптації стратегій під цільову аудиторію та використання креативних методів персоналізованого контенту. Ефективність візуального контенту з дронів визначається як сценарним підходом до відео, так і технічними характеристиками пристрою. Інтеграція високотехнологічного

обладнання дозволяє створити конкурентоспроможний відеопродукт, що посилює маркетинговий вплив на різні сегменти цільової аудиторії. Це відкриває нові можливості для побудови іміджу, формування довіри та стимулювання дії – зокрема, бронювання.

Ключові слова: готельний маркетинг, дрон-контент, поведінка споживача, цифрова реклама.

Problem statement. In the current conditions of digital transformation of the hospitality industry, visual content has become a key factor in attracting customers and forming a brand advantage. Today, innovative tools such as aerial photography from drones are gaining particular relevance, which allows creating unique visual impressions, demonstrating the benefits of the hotel in an emotionally attractive form. At the same time, there is a lack of systematic research that analyzes the real impact of such visual practices on the behavior of potential consumers. This creates a need for scientific understanding and marketing modeling of the effectiveness of using drone content in the hotel industry.

Analysis of recent research and publications. In modern scientific discourse, transformation processes in the hospitality industry under the influence of digitalization, globalization, and changes in consumer behavior were actively studied. Analysis of professional publications allows us to identify several key areas that form the scientific basis for studying the impact of visual content from drones on the behavior of potential customers.

In particular, I. Krupenna and M. Ostapenko, in the context of network forms of business, emphasize the need for visual brand identification as an element of the strategy for attracting customers [1]. I. Yegupova analyzes the components of the hospitality industry, outlining it as a multi-component sphere in which marketing tools, including visual content, are gaining increasing importance [2]. V. Paslavska, O. Orlova, and O. Basarab explore strategies for promoting the hotel business during a pandemic, emphasizing the need to update communication channels and increase

the visual attractiveness of the hospitality product [3]. I. Mendela and E. Mendela focus on innovative technologies that change the content and form of interaction with the client in the hotel sector [4]. N. Balatska, L. Radkevych, Y. Robul, O. Vdovichena, and A. Strenkovska substantiate the importance of digital marketing in creating new opportunities for the tourism business, including visual communications as a tool for emotional contact [5].

The work of A. Mazaraki, S. Melnychenko, and M. Danylenko outline the tools of Internet marketing that allow the hotel business to effectively communicate with the target audience, including aerial surveys, video content, and visualization of locations [6]. N. Sereda focuses on the adaptation of marketing strategies of the hospitality industry to the conditions of the post-war economy, emphasizing the role of flexibility, personalization, and digital technologies in attracting customers [7]. O. Listrova analyzes the tools of innovative marketing, among which visual content is of particular relevance as a component of branding and positioning of the hotel [8]. Zh. Garbar and Y. Hontaruk in their work prove the need to use non-standard visual approaches, including drones, to create a unique customer experience [9]. O. M. Sazonets, A.E. Gessen, O. V. Sedletska, and N. G. Yakovleva-Melnyk emphasize the role of graphic design in electronic marketing of hotel services, emphasizing the importance of photo and video content for forming a customer's first impression [10].

I. L. Sazonets and S. R. Zinkevich study public relations (PR) and advertising in the context of global challenges, emphasizing the impact of visual content on customer behavior and the creation of added value [11]. In his scientific work, Y. Palamarenko focuses on implementing innovative approaches in the strategic management of enterprises, emphasizing the importance of adapting to changes in the external environment and using the latest technologies to ensure competitiveness [12]. A. Bilgihan and P. Ricci highlight a new era of hotel marketing, where modern technologies - particularly virtual reality and artificial intelligence - become drivers of customer-oriented strategies [13]. The study by M. Byelikova et al. emphasizes

the importance of digital security and visual content in the context of the competitiveness of regions, especially coastal ones [14]. V. Shostak and O. Moskvich prove the effectiveness of creative marketing for destination development, where visualization of the territory through drones contributes to forming an emotional connection with the brand [15]. G. Volyanyk and N. Marushko consider tools for attracting and retaining customers, focusing on social networks and visualizing the service experience [16].

Analysis of sources shows that using drones in hotel business marketing strategies is only beginning to gain a systematic understanding in Ukrainian science. Although the issues of digital transformation, visual communication, and personalization are actively studied, the consumer's behavioral reaction to drone content remains insufficiently revealed. It is this gap that became the basis for our study.

Highlighting previously unresolved parts of the general problem. Despite the growing role of visual content in hotel marketing campaigns, its role as a behavioral trigger in booking decisions remains insufficiently studied. Existing publications mainly focus on the technical or aesthetic aspects of video recording, and much less often on the analysis of changes in consumer behavioral models under the influence of drone content. Thus, an in-depth analysis of drone visualization in hotel marketing through its impact on customer preferences, emotional involvement, and purchase intentions is relevant.

Formulation of the objectives of the article (task statement). This article aims to study the marketing potential of visual content shot with drones in shaping the behavior of potential customers in the field of hotel marketing. The main tasks are:

- to analyze digital channels of marketing communication in the hotel business;
- to identify key elements of visual content from drones in hotel marketing;

– to determine the key psychological and communication effects that drone content causes in the consumer and the behavioral reactions of potential customers to drone videos;

– to analyze strategic approaches to the use of drones and form a model of the influence of drone videos on customer behavior.

Presentation of the primary research material. In today's conditions of digital transformation and high competition in the hospitality industry, the search for practical marketing tools that can influence the emotions and behavior of potential customers is of particular importance. One such tool is drone content - visual materials shot with the help of drones, which allow hotel brands to present their space from a new perspective and create a sense of involvement even before the physical stay. The use of drone videos deserves special attention, which allow you to demonstrate not only the infrastructure, but also the atmosphere of the hotel space, and the quality of such content directly depends on the technical parameters of the drone - in particular, resolution, image stabilization, the ability to shoot in different lighting conditions and creative modes. These characteristics determine how aesthetically attractive and technologically convincing the video will look in the eyes of a potential customer, evoking a sense of presence.

We agree with the opinion of Krupenna I.A., Ostapenko M.E., who emphasize that the modern hospitality industry is undergoing a profound transformation, which includes changes in both the external marketing environment and internal business models, which is due to the dynamic growth of expectations of new generations of consumers, their desire for a unique and personalized experience, a decrease in loyalty to standard services, as well as the need to rethink the value of hotel service in the digital world, which is rapidly changing the rules of the game [1, p. 76].

In turn, researcher I. M. Yegupova, in her work, clarifies the conceptual boundaries of the hospitality industry as one of the key components of the modern service sector. Nowadays, marketing visualizations are becoming a tool not only for informing, but also for emotional engagement [2]. Visual content created with the

help of drones acquires special importance as an innovative tool of hotel marketing, combining digital technologies with elements of emotional involvement. Such visual solutions not only inform but also allow the formation of impressions and influence the perception and behavior of a potential client even before the actual visit to the establishment. In the hotel business, where the emotional component plays a decisive role in choosing a destination, drone content becomes part of a sensory strategy that covers visual, auditory, and intuitive channels of perception [3].

I. Ya. Mendela, E. M. Mendela notes that marketing innovations aimed at immersing the client in the establishment's atmosphere while planning the trip are essential to competitive advantage. In this context, the seven notes of hospitality, among which the visual impression takes the leading place, become the basis for forming a sustainable customer experience. Thus, using aerial and video materials as part of branding contributes to the growth of loyalty, emotional attachment, and making a favorable decision regarding booking [4, p. 23].

N. Balatska, L. Radkevych, Y. Robul, O. Vdovichena, and A. Strenkovska emphasize that digital technologies and digital marketing open up new opportunities for the development of tourism and hotel and restaurant business, in particular through the integration of visual content and personalized communication with customers [5]. We agree that these provisions emphasize adapting to digital trends and using innovative technologies to attract and retain customers. In the modern environment, marketing is becoming the basis for effective interaction of hotels with potential customers. It encompasses various digital platforms and tools that allow personalization of content, tracking customer behavior, reputation management, and targeted promotion. Visual content from drones is a component of this environment, which is formed by SEO (Search Engine Optimization) - optimized websites, social media, online booking systems, email marketing, and analytics tools (table 1).

The data presented demonstrate that drone content is integrated into a broad hotel marketing system and is not an isolated tool. Its use is possible in the brand's visual representation on social platforms and in email newsletters, on the main page

of the hotel website, or in targeted advertising. Drone video allows you to create a holistic image of the destination and contribute to forming an emotional connection with a potential client. It should be noted that the effectiveness of drone content increases precisely in the conditions of a multi-channel marketing strategy based on personalization, visual storytelling, and analytics of audience reactions.

Table 1

Digital marketing communication channels in the hotel business

Tool/channel	Role	Example of drone content integration
Hotel website	Main source of information, conversion	Video on the main page as a «hook video»
Instagram / Facebook	Visual image, brand storytelling	Drone videos + geotags + Reels
YouTube	Deep video engagement, SEO support	Full HD/4K hotel tour
Booking / TripAdvisor	Reviews + photos + emotional attachment	Inserting drone video into the hotel gallery
Email newsletters	Personalized communication with the client	Video selection of locations that motivates booking
PPC advertising/targeting	Rapid reach of the target audience through video ads	Advertising with short drone teasers
CRM- system	Management of customer base, loyalty	Tracking reactions to drone content

Source: formed by the author based on analysis [4;5]

Therefore, in modern conditions characterized by technological innovations, changing consumer preferences, globalization, and the consequences of pandemics, hotels and tourism enterprises must adapt their marketing strategies. These strategies should be flexible and focused on personalizing services, meeting changing customer needs, and implementing the latest technologies, such as data analysis, social networks, and digital channels [7].

The analysis of scientific literature has shown that in modern hotel marketing, visual content plays a crucial role in forming the first impression of the accommodation facility. Drone photography allows you to create unique visual images that combine aesthetics, spatial depth, and emotional effect. To systematize the visual elements that have the most significant impact on the behavior of a

potential client, we have summarized the key components of visual content from drones, which are most often used in promoting hotel products (table 2).

As can be seen from the table, the effectiveness of visual content is based not only on aesthetic appeal but also on the ability to evoke emotional reactions in the viewer, from a sense of scale and presence to increased interest in specific locations and hotel services. The compositional combination of frame dynamics, color scheme, and acoustic accompaniment plays a special role. Visual accents formed through drone filming are powerful for hotel branding, strengthening emotional contact with the audience even before physical contact with the service object. It should be noted that the quality of emotional engagement is primarily determined by the technical equipment used by the drones.

Table 2

Key elements of visual content from drones in hotel marketing

Content element	Description	Possible effect on the client
Panoramic overview	Shooting from above, covering the entire hotel area, beach, and pool	Forming a "scale effect", wow impression
Sunlight, color	Bright colors, sunset, turquoise sea	Aesthetic delight, association with relaxation
Frame dynamics	Smooth movement, zoom, flying over details	Feeling of presence, desire to "get there"
Music/sound	Melody or the sounds of nature	Increased emotional impact, relaxation
Focus on details	Bar, room, restaurant, SPA-zone	Stimulating interest in service, details

Source: author's development

Thus, the analyzed elements of visual content and behavioral reactions of potential customers allow us to conclude that the technical characteristics of drones (resolution, stabilization, shooting modes) directly affect the emotional effect and quality of visual perception. High-quality filming helps build trust and engagement, and increases the likelihood of booking, which enhances the marketing effectiveness of content. The study showed that innovative approaches in the field of hotel marketing help reduce the cost of providing services, strengthen the competitive

position of the establishment, and increase its reputation in the target market segment. [8, p. 106].

In today's world, booking a hotel is primarily shaped by visual content shared on social media. Platforms such as Instagram, Facebook, and X are both a means of communication and an effective channel for promoting hotel services. Creating attractive hotel pages and regularly updating content emphasizing unique visual advantages, including drone photography and videography, helps create a positive image and maintain customer loyalty [10].

It should be noted that one of the key advantages of visual content created using drones is its ability not only to inform, but also to influence the behavior of potential customers. In today's digital environment, visuals become triggers that trigger a range of cognitive, emotional, and behavioral responses. This opens up vast opportunities for hotel marketing to build trust, attract attention, and drive user action. Below are systematized typical behavioral reactions that a potential consumer may experience when watching drone videos and their external manifestations in the digital environment (table 3).

Table 3

Behavioral reactions of potential customers to drone videos

Behavioral reaction	Characteristics	External manifestation
Visual interest	First impression, visual engagement	Number of views, viewing duration
Emotional engagement	Aesthetic pleasure, peace, admiration	Likes, comments like "wow", "dream place"
Booking intention	The emergence of a desire to visit the hotel	Clicking on the link, viewing the price
Trust formation	Visual confirmation of quality	Positive reaction to comments, reposts
Brand recall	Memorability of the hotel image	Survey responses, logo/location recognition

Source: author's development

Thus, drone video performs not only an aesthetic or informative function but also serves as a tool for modeling the behavior of the target audience. Behavioral

reactions from simple viewing to the intention to make a reservation can be recorded and analyzed using digital indicators: views, likes, clicks on links, comments, and the level of interaction with content. This allows hotels to more accurately adjust their communication strategies and evaluate the effectiveness of visual marketing based on the real actions of potential customers.

Thus, the modern transformation of hotel marketing is determined by the interaction of many global factors: the growth of customer requirements for service quality, the development of digital technologies, the spread of individualized services, and the need for emotionally saturated visual contact with the brand. As noted by I. L. Sazonets and S. R. Zinkevich, hotel marketing today is not just a function of promoting services, but a holistic management system aimed at creating a valuable tourist product with a high level of personalization and technological content [11, p. 50].

In particular, within the framework of modern strategies, hotel enterprises are moving from unified approaches to dynamic models based on innovation, flexibility, franchising, and technological partnership, which creates new points of contact with the client. One of the key differentiation factors is the use of visual content, in particular aerial views from drones, which enhance PR effects and form unique associations with the brand, contributing to a more profound emotional attachment to the hotel.

We agree with the opinion of the scientist-economist Ya.V. Palamarenko, who emphasizes that the strategic development of a modern enterprise is impossible without integrating innovative solutions capable of adapting the organization to a rapidly changing market environment. In particular, there is a need to find marketing tools that simultaneously increase brand recognition, form a competitive advantage, and help attract new customers. These principles are continued in our research, where drone content is considered as an effective tool for strategic promotion in the hotel business [12].

In the context of increased competition in the hotel services market, the use of innovative tools, particularly visual content from drones, is an essential condition for an effective marketing strategy. However, shooting alone is not enough — the effectiveness of such a strategy depends on a competent combination of planning stages, targeting, emotional impact, analytics, and adaptation of content to the expectations of the target audience. Figure 1 presents a strategic approach to the use of drone video in hotel marketing.

Fig. 1. A strategic approach to using drone video in hotel marketing

Source: author's development

The proposed scheme reflects a comprehensive strategic approach to using drones in hotel marketing. It combines creative content creation with analytical mechanisms for managing interaction with the audience. Each stage—from defining the goal to the final increase in booking indicators—is interconnected with potential customers' behavioral reactions. This approach allows not only to strengthen the hotel's image but also to systematically increase the effectiveness of digital communications in the hospitality sector.

We have investigated the importance of digital tools – adaptive websites, SEO optimization, promotion through social networks, content marketing, and revenue analytics based on big data. That is why, in this context, visual content created using drones plays the role of not just an aesthetic element, but a key tool for forming engagement and emotional contact with the brand, which can become a catalyst for making a booking decision. Drones allow marketing communication to a new level, giving customers a "presence effect" even before they visit the hotel.

Therefore, in analyzing the features of the impact of visual content created using drones, it is advisable to highlight the key stages of transforming an aesthetic image into a specific behavioral reaction of a potential client. The created video sequence has an informative and psychological function: it evokes an emotional response, forms a brand image, and stimulates targeted action. Based on the systematization of visual effects, research into customer behavioral patterns and marketing patterns, a generalized model of the impact of drone content on the decision to choose a hotel was proposed (fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Model of the influence of drone video on customer behavior

Source: author's development

The proposed model shows that the emotional impact of video content from drones catalyzes the marketing process. The experienced visual emotions - admiration for the panorama, a sense of presence, aesthetic pleasure - contribute to strengthening trust in the brand, forming associations with comfort and quality of services. This, in turn, increases the likelihood of moving from interest to action - booking a room or searching for additional information about the facility. The model can be used as a conceptual basis for communication strategies in hotel marketing focused on the emotional engagement of customers.

Thus, creative marketing in the hospitality sector is a tool for forming the emotional attractiveness of territories, capable of influencing the motivation and choice of tourists by visualizing the uniqueness of destinations. Visual content, in particular from drones, influences the behavior of potential customers in hotel marketing because the facility's emotional immersion and creative presentation stimulate interest and decision-making about booking [15].

Forming effective marketing strategies in the hospitality industry is relevant due to its high dynamics, significant economic potential, and role in shaping the national image.

This industry provides significant revenue to the budget, creates new jobs, promotes intercultural exchange, and strengthens social integration. The successful functioning of hotel and tourism businesses today directly depends on the ability to implement innovative digital marketing tools and exceptionally personalized visual content, which allows not only to attract customers but also to maintain their loyalty [16].

Thus, the use of aerial photography and videography from drones opens up new opportunities to present a hotel product, form emotionally rich marketing communication, and increase the share of direct bookings. At the same time, a targeted approach allows you to adapt messages broadcast through social networks and websites to customers' real needs, increasing the overall effectiveness of hotel marketing.

Therefore, visual content from drones is an innovative channel of influence on a potential consumer within the framework of hotel product promotion. Such a creative marketing strategy allows you to form an attractive image of the destination, strengthen brand recognition, and create competitive advantages in the digital ecosystem of the hospitality industry.

Conclusions. The study made it possible to substantiate the importance of visual content, particularly videos and photos from drones, as an effective marketing tool in the hotel industry. In a modern information-rich environment where users make choices based on visual impressions, drones become a competitive advantage for hotels that seek to increase brand recognition, interest potential customers, and form an emotionally positive perception of services. Based on the analysis of scientific literature, it was found that visualization using drones: increases the level of trust in the hotel as a transparent, open service; contributes to the personalization of the customer experience by demonstrating the atmosphere, architecture, and natural surroundings; forms a positive brand image in social networks; is an effective tool for targeted promotion through video platforms and influencer marketing.

Thus, modern research indicates a transition from traditional marketing approaches to digital strategies focused on visual content. Using drones in this process should be considered an effective response to changing consumer behavioral patterns and the demand for visually rich communication.

It is advisable to direct further research prospects towards the development of effective algorithms for using visual content in complex digital and information and communication strategies, determining key indicators of drone video effectiveness, and studying the influence of cultural and demographic factors on the perception of visual content in hotel marketing.

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